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ROLE OF TECH SAVVYMILLENNIALS' IN ICT APPLICATION

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Abstract

21st century is known as the century of technologies due to the innovations that took place in this century. The Revolution in Industry (4IR) is transforming the industrial sector. As the change is inevitable, this new development is positively influencing various sectors. The popular industry standard, the buzzword "Industry 4.0" [1] is helping industries to adopt new technologies and automate the system. This growth is directly proportional to the need of techno skilled human resources. To fulfill this demand, the need of the generation, education institutions must and should upgrade self and adopt new standard popularly known as "Education 4.0". The progress in this aspect has catapulted the interest of stake holders. The affordability, reach, connectivity and many more factors are attracting the young minds to use technology in education sector. The ICT is playing a important role in this century of automation. Its application is found in Administration, Teaching, Learning, Evaluation and many more areas. The present generation students are technically strong compared to that of previous. The Generation-Z and Alpha are leading in usage of technology. The ICT application in education sector is discussed in this paper. The paper concludes with the contributions and influence of technocrat millennials' in successful implementation of ICT enabled services such as Flipped Learning, Blended Learning, STEM in education.

Keywords: Education 4.0, Millennials', ICT, Technocrats, Blended Learning**1. INTRODUCTION:**

Information and Communications Technology [2] is improving the social, economic and cultural life of the pupil. The inception of this education is changing the way, the education system is functioning. The approaches for new pedagogical innovations, research is changing due to the influence of ICT.

After the changes in policy of LPG (liberalization, Privatization and Globalization) in India, the education sector has seen a sea change due to the expanded market for technology driven educators. The ICT application has widened its horizons and its vast application can be traced in teaching, learning, content delivery mechanisms. The technology driven ICT can give solution for issues of access and thus resolves the issues of digital divide.

1.1 About Industrial Revolution [3]

The industry standard denotes the changes in overall functionality and usage of new concepts, starting from Research and Development to Post Sales Service and Maintenance. It proposes the globally acceptable concepts to be adopted and followed by the Industry.

Industrial Revolution-1

- Machinery usage for Quick Production

Industrial Revolution-2

- Electric power usage for mass production.

Industrial Revolution-3

- Electronics and Information Technology usage to automate the production.

Industrial Revolution-4

- Internet of Technology [4], Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Machine Learning, Autonomous Vehicles, Bio Nanotechnology, 3D printing, material science, Quantum computing, Energy storage are used.

[Fig 1.0 Industrial Revolution Phases]

Technology adoption in industry has created a new wave called Industry Revolution. This wave is so strong that, the change is inevitable [5]. Technical evaluation is accelerating the pace of change. The change which was measured in terms of Centuries, years, is now measured in Months.

The IR 4.0 is positively influencing the Techno Job market. The innovation and development in automation fields such as Internet of Things, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence etc are reducing the human force. At the same time, new jobs will crop up with new skills and EQ.

The Industry 4.0 is driven by Internet of Things. In the technology enabled education institutions, The processing of continuous data stream matters the most. The Education 4.0 deals with processing of these sorts of data and generating the valuable outcome.

2ICTAPPLICATION AREAS [6]

The education 4.0 is helping education industry to upgrade qualitatively and quantitatively. It is also supporting institutions to adopt new strategies for effective

implementation of administration through smart means. Thus education 4.0 [7] will help the educational institutions for its holistic development. As the 21st century education is witnessing change from Trainer's centered to Learner's Centered system, new methods, policies, strategies can be seen. The below is the list of areas where ICT application is present in terms of learning.

1. Learning can taken place anywhere anytime.

E-learning tools - Self paced learning - Remote learning - Flipped classroom - Interactive learning

2. Personalized learning

Specialized training - Enforcing positive learning experience

3. Choice for students to determine how they want to learn.

BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) approach - Blended learning - Flipped classroom[8]
- DIY Approach

4. Project based learning

Short term projects - Opportunity to apply knowledge and skills - Enhancement of organizational collaborative, time management skills

5. Hands on learning

Field experience - Internships - Mentoring projects - Collaborating projects - Face to face interaction

6. Exposure of data interpretation

Applying theoretical knowledge numbers - Reasoning skills

7. Individualized Assessment

Assessment of students factual knowledge - Assessment of application of knowledge

8. Students Input in curriculum framing.

- Taking inputs from curriculum designers as well as students helps to bring practicality.
- Feedback from students to update on continues basis.

9. Self paced learning facility for the Students.

Teachers to assume new role of facilitators - Guiding students through their learning process. Students learn things as per their needs.

3.TECH SAVVY MILLANNIALS' :

The technology has become the basic need for Millennials'. As quoted above the rapid development in technology has flooded the e-gadgets in the market which is the part and parcel of the Young Minds.

The way of leading social life has literally changed due to the invent of the hand held mobile telephone. People started preferring text communication than the voice which was the most favorite once upon a time. The technology has influenced the childhood adolescence and adulthood of millennials'.

4. Technology in the Classroom & Workplace

The millennials' have experienced technology aided learning in classroom which has a sea difference from traditional learning methods. They have experienced students focused learning through the usage of technologies such as smart digital boards, e-assignments, computer assisted learning, computer aided learning even online learning benefits.

These have made millennials' to experience real life environment, the real world opportunities in four walls. The simulation tool based practical learning has made students to gain access to educational equipments easily.

Generation-Z students prefer [9]

Hands-on experience/ learning - They welcome challenges - Group discussion - Interactive learning environment learning without boundaries (anytime anywhere) - Complete access to the educational resources - Unlimited access to the updated information –Easy connectivity with the members. Usage of digital tools –Online forums for updated the resources.

Generation Name	Birth Year
The Lost Generation	1890 – 1915
The Inter bellum Generation	1901 – 1913
The Greatest Generation	1910 – 1924
The Silent Generation	1925 – 1945
The Baby Boomer Generation	1946 – 1964
The Baby Bust Generation – Gex X	1965 – 1979
The Xennials	1975 – 1985
The Millenials Gen-Y	1980 – 1995
Generation Z	1996 – 2010
Generation Alpha	2011 – 2025

Fig 2.0: Generations [7]

4. Generation Alpha [10]:

This generation is also known as “Children of Millennials”. This is the first generation born entirely within the 21st century. Pupils of this generation are totally smart as they are younger than the Smart Mobiles. Their generation is very special due to the excessive innovations and developments. They are enjoying the fruits of efforts put by the previous generations. Their day begins with Mobile and Ends with same. This generation is focusing much on safety parameters too though the usage of techno tools. The pupils are getting access to the hand held devices in their early age. This is making them smart day by day.

5. 21st Century Skills:

This century is the century of skills. The technology and Internet is changing the way world is growing. The education is reshaping due to the application of information and communication technology. The proper implementation of these is possible when the stake holders possess the necessary skills. The millennials’ should incorporate the skills to survive in the current techno generation.

The 21st Century skill can be classified into following categories: [11]

➤ **Learning skills:** It teaches students about the mental processes.

- **Literacy skills:** Skills related to the education
- **Life skills:** Additional skills needed to lead life.

Learning Skills: This has four sub skills. Such as

- **Critical thinking:** Finding solutions to problems
- **Creativity:** Thinking outside the box
- **Collaboration:** Working with others
- **Communication:** Talking to others

Literacy Skills: (IMT Skills)

- **Information literacy:** Understanding facts, figures, statistics, and data
- **Media literacy:** Understanding the methods and outlets in which information is published
- **Technology literacy:** Understanding the machines that make the Information Age possible

Life Skills: Additional skills needed to lead life.

- **Flexibility:** Deviating from plans as needed
- **Leadership:** Motivating a team to accomplish a goal
- **Initiative:** Starting projects, strategies, and plans on one's own
- **Productivity:** Maintaining efficiency in an age of distractions
- **Social skills:** Meeting and networking with others for mutual benefit

6. Technologies for Millennials'

As the young generation is more attracted towards the usage of e-gadgets, they are familiar about its pros and cons and variety applications. The technology enabled young generation uses various techno tools frequently. It has got its own reasons. First and foremost is the affordability and then comes simplicity. The frequently used application tools are as follows.

Linked-in

This is the application which can be used for professional communication. Here the candidates register themselves, share and access the professional information. The young generation likes this due to its simplicity and the interactive.

Blogger

This tool helps to create and manage the blog. It is another commonly used tools which helps to post the contents easily.

Wordpress

Website creation has become the hobby for 21st century students. They create websites as if it is created by some web designer professionals. There are many applications which helps to develop websites with or without coding.

Whatsapp

This generation stakeholders are preferring text based communication than voice based. Now the trend has changed to integrated style. The combination of audio, video and text is much effective than that of the traditional system of communication.

Instagram

The technology has contributed a lot to the multimedia sector. The availability of high resolution camera phones, cloud storage facility has made people to lean towards the usage of pictures for every occasions. Considering the interest and need of this generation, people have come up with new application tools. This is one such tool which helps people to share their real time pictures.

Twitter

This is the century of Quick and Short communication. This application helps the people to communicate better and convey the information very quickly.

Hangout

To connect people live with video streaming, this application is highly used. There are several similar applications which can be used to achieve the desired objectives. Out of which the hangout stands high. The young generation uses this for many constructive applications such as group discussions, even it can be used for education purpose too.

Team Viewer

The computer resources to be shared with other remote systems. There are many applications which does this. The team viewer helps people to access the remote system, to witness the remote computer screen and take the suitable actions if any.

YouTube

The video based files can be accessed shared viewed through the application called youtube. There are number of similar applications, the common attributes and simplicity has made what you tube is.

7. Introduction to Seachers:

The word may sound very different. Yes it's very true. Thanks to the technology for this. The students are transforming to teachers due to the easily available techno tools, the repository of knowledge, the knowledge hub. Thus student-teachers (searchers) are coming up in large numbers.

The following applications / tools can be used by the teachers to transform themselves to technology enabled teachers.

- do-pdf
- YouTube Downloader
- Screen Recorder
- Mentoring Tutors

8. STEM Education [12]:The technological advancement is transforming the world. The application is highly found in the four core areas such as Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. Usually the Primary and Secondary curriculum focuses on these areas

which are the mandatory subjects to be studied in detail. The development in technology has doubled the importance of these concepts as we are shifting ourself from natural intelligence to artificial intelligence aspects. These new developments have uplifted the importance of STEM.

Contemporary Aspects of STEM Education [13]

STEM Education is gaining the popularity day by day. The pedagogy and the methodology for training implementing the STEM Education among the stakeholders to be done with special measures.

STEM Fields Defined

The four strands of STEM; Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, have been staple forms of all students' academic careers; particularly science and mathematics. They are defined as:

- Science: the systematic study of the nature and behavior of the material and physical universe, based on observation, experiment, and measurement, and the formulation of laws to describe these facts in general terms (Science, 2012).
- Technology: the branch of knowledge that deals with the creation and use of technical means and their interrelation with life, society, and the environment, drawing upon such subjects as industrial arts, engineering, applied science, and pure science (Technology, 2012).
- Engineering: the art or science of making practical application of the knowledge of pure sciences, as physics or chemistry, as in the construction of engines, bridges, buildings, mines, ships, and chemical plants (Engineering, 2012).
- Mathematics: a group of related sciences, including algebra, geometry, and calculus, concerned with the study of number, quantity, shape, and space and their interrelationships by using a specialized notation (Mathematics, 2012).

9. CONCLUSION:

The paper describes how the technology can shape the educational institutions with special focus on implementation of technology in Teaching, Learning and also administration. The general overview of various generations pertaining to technology usage is discussed here. The outcome of the literature study focuses on ICT application possibilities by Tech-Savvy millennials'. The young generation talents choice of technology is also discussed here with special focus on STEM Learning using ICT.

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